

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data standardization

ADOPTED:
25 October 2023

ADOPTING BODY:
Genebank Information
Systems Team

LAST UPDATED:
25 October 2023

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data standardization

About this document

This document is part of a webinar series organized by the Genesys team in 2023 on passport data preparation for publication in Genesys. The series covers practical approaches to data cleaning, standardization to MCPD v.2.1, validation, and eventual publication in Genesys, with a particular focus on genebanks managing passport data in spreadsheets such as Microsoft Excel.

This publication accompanies Part 2 of the series, which focused on data cleaning and standardization prior to validation and publication.

This guidance is intended as a practical, step-by-step resource that participants can follow alongside the webinar recording or apply directly to their own datasets.

Webinar resources

Webinar recording:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YJA8QPrOYok>

Related documents in this series:

Part 1 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data cleaning

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/ak2d6y1hu9za4e830924r7508motvm49>

Part 3 – Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data validation

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/7hnoxv38qovsfhtu4uqvnyi1doa9xe98>

For questions, support, or to request the sample data file used during the training sessions, please contact: helpdesk@genesys-pgr.org

Guidance on passport data preparation using Excel: Data standardizing

After applying these steps you will be able to prepare your data for validation.

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12- Preparing useful lookup tables for column labels

The purpose of this step is to create tables that contain a list all your original column headers, matched with their MCPD spelling.

Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
GHA091	OS-102	Oryza	sativa	20120100	21	100	1
GHA091	OS-103	Oryza	sativa	20131205	61	100	1
GHA091	OS-104	Oryza	sativa	20131205	21	300	1
GHA091	OS-105	Oryza	sativa	20131205	26	300	1
GHA091	OS-106	Manihot	esculenta	20120100	40	400	0
GHA091	OS-107	Manihot	esculenta	20120100	23	300	0
GHA091	OS-108	Manihot	esculenta	20131205	26	500	0

In your Original data file, select all the column titles, and copy them by pressing **Ctrl+C**

Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

In a new Excel file dedicated for lookup tables, transpose the data you copied by right-clicking where you want to paste the list of column names, then choose Transpose:

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Excel interface with the 'Home' tab selected. The 'Paste' dropdown menu is open, and the 'Transpose' option is highlighted in green. The spreadsheet below shows the following data:

Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

12- Preparing useful lookup tables for column labels

Next to the transposed column names, add their matching MCPD v.2.1 title in another column.

You can access the MCPD v.2.1 standard in this link:

<https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/publications-data/faobioiversity-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-v21-mcpd-v21-december-2015>

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Institute	INSTCODE			
2	Accession Number	ACCENUMB			
3	Genus	GENUS			
4	Species	SPECIES			
5	Acquisition date	ACQDATE			
6	Collecting source	COLLSRC			
7	Biological status	SAMPSTAT			
8	Status in the MLS	MLSSTAT			
9					
10					
11					

You can clear formats of the transposed data by checking page 12 of the documentation on part 1:

<https://croptrust.box.com/s/ak2d6y1hu9za4e830924r7508motvm49>

Select both columns, your original column names and their MCPD match, and create an Excel Table by clicking **Ctrl+T**:

	A	B	C	D	E
1	Institute	INSTCODE			
2	Accession Number	ACCENUMB			
3	Genus	GENUS			
4	Species	SPECIES			
5	Acquisition date	ACQDATE			
6	Collecting source	COLLSRC			
7	Biological status	SAMPSTAT			
8	Status in the MLS	MLSSTAT			
9					
10					
11					

Ctrl+T

Create Table

Where is the data for your table?

My table has headers

If you titled these columns, then make sure to tick this box.

12- Preparing useful lookup tables for column labels

By creating an Table without headers, Excel will automatically add the headers titled "Column 1" and "Column 2", and assign a formatting usually in the blue and white colors. You can always change the column headers and table formatting colors.

Column1	Column2
Institute	INSTCODE

My original column names	Their MCPD matching names
Institute	INSTCODE
Accession Number	ACCENUMB
Genus	GENUS

You can find more information on Excel tables in this link:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/overview-of-excel-tables-7ab0bb7d-3a9e-4b56-a3c9-6c94334e492c>

Save this new file as we will add more sheets to it later. In this document we will refer to it as **File 1**.

What we just did is create a lookup table, that will be used later to automatically match the column headers to their MCPD names.

The work we did now is manual, but it saves time and avoids errors for later, especially when your data is in many different Excel files.

13- Preparing useful lookup tables for coded values

The purpose of this step is to create a table that contains a list all your original data values, matched with their MCPD coded values (for example **wild material** is coded as **100** in MCPD). This matching is done for every column separately.

Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
GHA091	OS-102	Oryza	sativa	20120100	21	100	1
GHA091	OS-103	Oryza	sativa	20131205	61	100	1
GHA091	OS-104	Oryza	sativa	20131205	21	300	1
GHA091	OS-105	Oryza	sativa	20131205	26	300	1
GHA091	OS-106	Manihot	esculenta	20120100	40	400	0
GHA091	OS-107	Manihot	esculenta	20120100	23	300	0
GHA091	OS-108	Manihot	esculenta	20131205	26	500	0

In your Original data file, select the values of the column, and copy them by pressing **Ctrl+C**

Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

In **File 1** dedicated for lookup tables (refer to Step 1), paste the data you copied by right-clicking where you want to paste the list of column names, then choose Paste Values:

13- Preparing useful lookup tables for coded values

Next to the pasted data values, add their matching MCPD v.2.1 coded values in another column.

You can access the MCPD v.2.1 standard in this link:

<https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/publications-data/faobioiversity-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-v21-mcpd-v21-december-2015>

2.4 Select both columns, your original column names and their MCPD match, and create an Excel Table by clicking **Ctrl+T**:

Ctrl+T

If you titled these columns, then make sure to tick this box.

13- Preparing useful lookup tables for coded values

By creating an Table without headers, Excel will automatically add the headers titled "Column 1" and "Column 2", and assign a formatting usually in the blue and white colors. You can always change the column headers and table formatting colors.

The screenshot shows the Excel ribbon with the 'Table' tab selected. The 'Table Name' is set to 'Table2'. The ribbon includes options for 'Summarise with Pivot Table', 'Remove Duplicates', and 'Convert to Range'. The status bar at the bottom indicates 'Update Available' and 'We've made some fixes and improvements'.

Column1	Column2
wild	100

My original values for biological status	Their MCPD matching codes
wild	100

You can find more information on Excel tables in this link:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/overview-of-excel-tables-7ab0bb7d-3a9e-4b56-a3c9-6c94334e492c>

Save this as a new sheet in **File 1**.

What we just did is create a lookup table, that will be used later to automatically match your biological status values to their MCPD names (SAMPSTAT).

The work we did now is manual, but it saves time and avoids errors for later, especially when your data is in many different Excel files.

You can apply the same steps for the values of Collecting Source (COLLSRC), Storage type (STORAGE), and status in the MLS (MLSSTAT).

MCPD v.2.1 coded values for **biological status** of the accession (**SAMPSTAT**):

The coding scheme proposed can be used at 3 different levels of detail: either by using the general codes (in boldface) such as 100, 200, 300, 400, or by using the more specific codes such as 110, 120, etc.

100) Wild

110) Natural

120) Semi-natural/wild

130) Semi-natural/sown

200) Weedy

300) Traditional cultivar/landrace

400) Breeding/research material

410) Breeder's line

411) Synthetic population

412) Hybrid

413) Founder stock/base population

414) Inbred line (parent of hybrid cultivar)

415) Segregating population

416) Clonal selection

420) Genetic stock

421) Mutant (e.g. induced/insertion mutants, tilling populations)

422) Cytogenetic stocks (e.g. chromosome addition/substitution, aneuploids, amphiploids)

423) Other genetic stocks (e.g. mapping populations)

500) Advanced or improved cultivar (conventional breeding methods)

600) GMO (by genetic engineering)

999) Other (Elaborate in REMARKS field)

MCPD v.2.1 coded values for the **type of germplasm storage** (**STORAGE**):

If germplasm is maintained under different types of storage, multiple choices are allowed, separated by a semicolon (e.g. 20;30). (Refer to FAO/IPGRI Genebank Standards 1994 for details on storage type.)

10) Seed collection

11) Short term

12) Medium term

13) Long term

20) Field collection

30) In vitro collection

40) Cryopreserved collection

50) DNA collection

99) Other (elaborate in REMARKS field)

You can access the MCPD v.2.1 standard in this link:

<https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/publications-data/faobioiversity-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-v21-mcpd-v21-december-2015>

MCPD v.2.1 coded values for **the collecting source** of the accession (**COLLSRC**):

The coding scheme proposed can be used at 2 different levels of detail: either by using the general codes (in boldface) such as 10, 20, 30, 40, etc., or by using the more specific codes, such as 11, 12, etc.

- 10) Wild habitat**
 - 11) Forest or woodland
 - 12) Shrubland
 - 13) Grassland
 - 14) Desert or tundra
 - 15) Aquatic habitat
- 20) Farm or cultivated habitat**
 - 21) Field
 - 22) Orchard
 - 23) Backyard, kitchen or home garden (urban, peri-urban or rural)
 - 24) Fallow land
 - 25) Pasture
 - 26) Farm store
 - 27) Threshing floor
 - 28) Park
- 30) Market or shop**
- 40) Institute, Experimental station, Research organization, Genebank**
- 50) Seed company**
- 60) Weedy, disturbed or ruderal habitat**
 - 61) Roadside
 - 62) Field margin
- 99) Other (Elaborate in REMARKS field)**

MCPD v.2.1 coded values for the status of the accession in the **Multilateral System (MLSSTAT)**:

The status of an accession with regards to the Multilateral System (MLS) of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture. Leave the value empty if the status is not known.

- 0) No (not included)**
- 1) Yes (included)**
- 99) Other (elaborate in REMARKS field, e.g. 'under development')**

You can access the MCPD v.2.1 standard in this link:

<https://alliancebioiversityciat.org/publications-data/faobioiversity-multi-crop-passport-descriptors-v21-mcpd-v21-december-2015>

14- Existing lookup tables online

The previous steps showed how you can map the column headers and coded values to MCPD v.2.1 through lookup tables.

This step links you to some databases where you can extract data to keep it at hand, also to be used as a lookup table.

The FAO WIEWS database helps you validate and map the following columns:

- Collecting institute code (**COLLCODE**)
- Collecting institute name (**COLLNAME**)
- Breeding institute code (**BREDCODE**)
- Breeding institute name (**BREDNAME**)
- Donor institute code (**DONORCODE**)
- Donor institute name (**DONORNAME**)
- Location of safety duplicates (**DUPLSITE**)
- Institute maintaining safety duplicates (**DUPLINSTNAME**)

Find it at: <https://www.fao.org/wiews/data/organizations/en/>

The screenshot shows the search interface for the FAO WIEWS database. It features several input fields for search criteria: 'Name of organization', 'Organization acronym', 'WIEWS instcode', 'City', 'Country', and 'Organization role(s)'. A dropdown menu for 'Valid/invalidated organizations' is set to 'Valid only', with a callout box stating 'Make sure that you select "validated only"'. A search button with a magnifying glass icon is highlighted with a yellow circle and a hand icon. Below the search form, the 'Results' section shows a 'Back to Search' button, a 'Download Results' button with a download icon, and a pagination control showing 'Showing 1 to 25 of 18608 rows' with page numbers 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, and 745. A yellow circle and hand icon highlight the 'Download Results' button.

Search

Name of organization:

Organization acronym:

WIEWS instcode:

City:

Country:

Organization role(s):

Valid/invalidated organizations:

Make sure that you select "validated only"

Results

Back to Search

Download Results

Showing 1 to 25 of 18608 rows

< 1 2 3 4 5 ... 745 >

14- Existing lookup tables online

The list of countries matched to their ISO codes helps you validate and map this column:

- Country of origin (**ORIGCTY**)

Find it at:

<https://github.com/luke/ISO-3166-Countries-with-Regional-Codes/blob/master/all/all.csv>

1

Ctrl+C

name	alpha-2	alpha-3	country-code	iso_3166-2	region	sub-region	intermediate-region	region-code	sub-region-code
Afghanistan	AF	AFG	004	ISO 3166-2:AF	Asia	Southern Asia		142	034
Åland Islands	AX	ALA	248	ISO 3166-2:AX	Europe	Northern Europe		150	154
Albania	AL	ALB	008	ISO 3166-2:AL	Europe	Southern Europe		150	039
Algeria	DZ	DZA	012	ISO 3166-2:DZ	Africa	Northern Africa		002	015
American Samoa	AS	ASM	016	ISO 3166-2:AS	Oceania	Polynesia		009	061
Andorra	AD	AND	020	ISO 3166-2:AD	Europe	Southern Europe		150	039
Angola	AO	AGO	024	ISO 3166-2:AO	Africa	Sub-Saharan Africa	Middle Africa	002	202
Anguilla	AI	AIA	660	ISO 3166-2:AI	Americas	Latin America and the Caribbean	Caribbean	019	419
Antarctica	AQ	ATA	010	ISO 3166-2:AQ					
Antigua and Barbuda	AG	ATG	028	ISO 3166-2:AG	Americas	Latin America and the Caribbean	Caribbean	019	419

2

Ctrl+V
in Excel

name	alpha-2	alpha-3	country-code	iso_3166-2	region	sub-region	intermediate-region	region-code	sub-region-code	intermediate-region-code
Afghanistan	AF	AFG	4	ISO 3166-2:A	Asia	Southern Asia		142	34	
Åland Islands	AX	ALA	248	ISO 3166-2:A	Europe	Northern Europe		150	154	
Albania	AL	ALB	8	ISO 3166-2:A	Europe	Southern Europe		150	39	
Algeria	DZ	DZA	12	ISO 3166-2:C	Africa	Northern Africa		2	15	
American Sa	AS	ASM	16	ISO 3166-2:A	Oceania	Polynesia		9	61	

14- Existing lookup tables online

The list of predefined datums that can be used in coordinate system definitions helps you validate and map this column:

- Coordinate datum (**COORDDATUM**)

Find it at:

https://docs.safe.com/fme/html/FME_Desktop_Documentation/FME_Desktop/CoordSys/Predefined_Datums.htmv

SAFE SOFTWARE

Search FME Desktop help

Predefined Datums

These tables list the predefined datums that can be used in coordinate system definitions. Note that each coordinate system definition must specify either a datum or an ellipsoid.

Datum	Description
ABIDJAN1987	Abidjan 1987
ABIDJAN-87	Abidjan 1987, Ivory Coast (replaces Locodjo)
ACCRA	Accra 1929, Ghana
ACCRA1929	Accra 1929 modified, Ghana
ADINDAN	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), mean for Ethiopia and Sudan
ADINDAN-B	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Burkina Faso
ADINDAN-E	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Ethiopia
ADINDAN-M	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Mali
ADINDAN-S	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Senegal
ADINDAN-SU	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Sudan
ADIND-C	Adindan (Blue Nile 1958), Cameroon
ADIND-M	Adindan, mean for Burkina Faso, Guinea, Mali and Senegal

It is easier to save all these lookup tables in different sheets located in the same file, or in separate files located in the same folder for quick access.

Please note that all these lists are subject to updates or changes over time. It is recommended to revisit the source link, and apply the same steps above to update your lookup tables (once per year for example).

Mapping your data to MCPD using lookup tables

In steps 1 and 3 we created the lookup tables that will help you map some of your passport data to MCPD v.2.1. The rest of the passport data mapping usually happens without lookup tables because of the high variability in the values (all data related to dates such as Acquisition Date ACQDATE and Collecting Date COLLDATE as well as Taxonomy data and geographic coordinates).

This step will first show you how to map the column headers and coded values using lookup tables, then the other data types.

15- Mapping column headers using the lookup tables

Copy the passport data sheet to a new one, and select all the column headers and insert a new row above them:

In the new row, use the VLOOKUP function in Excel to match your column headers with their MCPD titles that you prepared in Step 1, referred to in this document as **File 1**.

For that, type in the new row: **=VLOOKUP(**

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	=VLOOKUP(
2	Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
3	National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
4	National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
5	National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
6	National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
7	National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
8	National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
9	National Genebank	OS-108	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

15- Mapping column headers using the lookup tables

This starts the function that has 4 fields to fill out, each one is separated from the other by a comma (,):

- The first field is the cell that contains the value you want to lookup (your original column header). In this document, the cell is [A2](#). Click on [A2](#) and add a comma and a space.

So now the formula is **=VLOOKUP(A2,**

- The second field is the range that contains the lookup value with its match (**File 1**)

Without pressing any other button on the keyboard, go to that file and select all the table in it and press Enter then add a comma and a space. This will automatically add the range to your formula which will be become:

=VLOOKUP(A2, Table1[#All],

- The third field is the column number in the range containing the return value. If you followed Step 1, then it would be the second column in **File 1**. So type 2 and space in the formula which will become:

=VLOOKUP(A2, Table1[#All], 2,

- The last field is an indication whether the match is approximate or exact. In this case we want to use an exact match, so type FALSE and close the parentheses.

The final lookup formula is:

=VLOOKUP(A2, Table1[#All], 2, FALSE)

Press Enter, and the MCPD match should appear.

15- Mapping column headers using the lookup tables

Click and drag the formula horizontally, across all of the empty first row:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	INSTCODE	ACCENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
2	Institute	Accession Number	Genus	Species	Acquisition date	Collecting source	Biological status	Status in the MLS
3	National Genebank	OS-102	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	included
4	National Genebank	OS-103	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
5	National Genebank	OS-104	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	included
6	National Genebank	OS-105	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
7	National Genebank	OS-106	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
8	National Genebank	OS-107	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included

💡 You can find more information on the Click and Drag functionality in this link:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/copy-a-formula-by-dragging-the-fill-handle-in-excel-for-mac-dd928259-622b-473f-9a33-83aa1a63e218>

Now you have matched your original column names in the second row to their MCPD titles in the first row. But if you click on any of the new titles, you will see the formula in the formula bar.

This means that when you delete the original column title, the mapped one will be show an error **#N/A**

	A	B	
1	#N/A	ACCENUMB	G
2		Accession Number	G
3	National Genebank	OS-102	O

In order to avoid this, you need to select the first row that contains the mapped column titles, copy it, then use a special pasting option called Paste Values:

The screenshot shows the Microsoft Excel interface with the 'Home' tab selected. A context menu is open over the spreadsheet, showing various paste options. The 'Paste Values' option is highlighted with a hand cursor. The spreadsheet data is visible in the background, showing columns D through H with headers like SPECIES, ACQDATE, COLLSRC, SAMPSTAT, and MLSSTAT.

15- Mapping column headers using the lookup tables

Now that your column headers are mapped to MCPD and unlinked from the formula, you may delete the second row that contains your original column headers.

We recommend that you keep a copy of your original data stored in a safe location. This is important to run quality checks at a later stage. So don't forget to copy your original sheet to a new file before mapping to MCPD.

The VLOOKUP function is instead:

- BUSCARV in Spanish
- RECHERCHEV in French

16- Mapping coded values using the lookup tables

As per the previous step, we are now working in a copy of your original file. In this copy file, you already applied the mapping to the column header, now you want to map the values of the column that have codes in MCPD.

For that, select the column you want to apply the mapping to, copy it, right click on the column next to it and click on Insert Copied Cells. Don't worry that this will override the data in other columns, as this functionality will add a new column and insert the copied cells there.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H
1	INSTCODE	ACCENUMB			DATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
2	National Genebank	OS-102			Jan-12	Field	wild	included
3	National Genebank	OS-103			December 2013	Roadside	Wild	included
4	National Genebank	OS-104			December 2013	from field	landrace	included
5	National Genebank	OS-105			December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	included
6	National Genebank	OS-106			Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	not included
7	National Genebank	OS-107			Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	not included
8	National Genebank	OS-108			December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	not included

16- Mapping coded values using the lookup tables

Now that your column headers are mapped to MCPD and unlinked from the formula, you may delete the second row that contains your original column headers.

 It is better to copy the cell you want to map than over ride it in order to run a quality check to validate your mapping to MCPD against the original data.

In the new column, use the VLOOKUP function that is detailed in Step 4.1 to match your values with their codes in MCPD using the lookup tables you created in Step 2.

We will use the example of biological status (SAMPSTAT) values. Copy this column and insert the copied cells next to it as we saw earlier:

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	ENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
2	02	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	wild	included
3	03	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	Wild	included
4	04	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	landrace	included
5	05	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	Land Race	included
6	06	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	Breeding material	not included
7	07	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	Landrace	not included
8	08	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	improved cultivar	not included

In the first cell of the copied column, type **=VLOOKUP(** then press on the first cell of the original column and press comma and space, in this data sample file, the function will become **=VLOOKUP(G2,**

Now you want to select the lookup table you created for the biological status of accessions. Go to that sheet, and select it all:

	A	B	C	D
1	Column1	Column2		
2	wild	100		
3	Wild	100		
4	landrace	300		
5	Land Race	300		
6	Breeding material	400		
7	Landrace	300		
8	improved cultivar	500		
9				

16- Mapping coded values using the lookup tables

After selecting the lookup table, press Enter, then add a comma and a space. In this sample file, the formula becomes **=VLOOKUP(G2, Table2[#All],**

Since the values I want the formula to return are located in the second column of my lookup table, I add 2 and a comma and a space, then type FALSE and close the parentheses because I want the formula to lookup exact matches, not approximate ones.

The final formula in this sample becomes **=VLOOKUP(G2, Table2[#All], 2, FALSE)**

Press Enter after closing the parentheses. Now you should see a coded value instead of the text (for example instead of **wild**, you now have the number **100**).

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	ENUMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
2	02	ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	100	included
3	03	oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	Wild	included
4	04	Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	landrace	included
5	05	ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	Land Race	included
6	06	manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	Breeding material	not included
7	07	MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	Landrace	not included
8	08	Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	improved cultivar	not included

Click and Drag the cell that contains the function across all the copied biological status (SAPMSTAT) column:

	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
	IMB	GENUS	SPECIES	ACQDATE	COLLSRC	SAMPSTAT	SAMPSTAT	MLSSTAT
		ORYZA	sativa	Jan-12	Field	wild	100	included
		oryza	sativa	5 December 2013	Roadside	Wild	100	included
		Oryza	Sativa	5 December 2013	from field	landrace	300	included
		ORYZA	Sativa	5 December 2013	Farmstore	Land Race	300	included
		manihot	esculenta	Jan-12	Breeding institute	Breeding material	400	not included
		MANIHOT	Esculenta	Jan-12	Backyard	Landrace	300	not included
		Manihot	ESCULENTA	5 December 2013	farm store	improved cultivar	500	not included

You can find more information on the Click and Drag functionality in this link:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/copy-a-formula-by-dragging-the-fill-handle-in-excel-for-mac-dd928259-622b-473f-9a33-83aa1a63e218>

17- Disconnect data from function

After applying any function to a column, for example in the previous step 16, this column will become linked to the original data.

If you delete the original Collecting source column, your new COLLSRC column will show values as an error: **#REF!**

The diagram illustrates the effect of deleting the source data. On the left, a table with columns 'Collecting source' and 'COLLSRC' is shown. The 'Collecting source' column is highlighted with a yellow box and a large yellow 'X' is drawn over it, indicating its deletion. A yellow arrow points from this table to the right, where a new table is shown. This new table has a header 'COLLSRC' and ten rows, each containing the error message '#REF!'.

Collecting source	COLLSRC
Field	21
Roadside	61
from field	21
Farmstore	26
Breeding institute	40
Backyard	23
farm store	26

COLLSRC
#REF!

In order to avoid that, you may disconnect the data in the COLLSRC column from the function by applying the following steps:

Select all the data in the SAMPSTAT column by clicking on the first cell, then **Ctrl Shift down**

Collecting source	COLLSRC
Field	21
Roadside	61
from field	21
Farmstore	26
Breeding institute	40
Backyard	23
farm store	26

17- Disconnect data from function

While your selection of the SAMPSTAT data is active, copy the data by pressing **Ctrl C**, then go to the Home ribbon and press on **Paste Values**:

Now you have disconnected your values from the function, and in case you delete your original column, there won't be any **#REF!** error replacing your data.

Mapping other data types

The previous steps showcased how these passport data descriptors can be mapped to MCPD v.2.1 using lookup tables:

- Collecting institute code (**COLLCODE**)
- Collecting institute name (**COLLNAME**)
- Breeding institute code (**BREDCODE**)
- Breeding institute name (**BREDNAME**)
- Donor institute code (**DONORCODE**)
- Donor institute name (**DONORNAME**)
- Location of safety duplicates (**DUPLSITE**)
- Institute maintaining safety duplicates (**DUPLINSTNAME**)

Mapping other data types

This step will show different methods for mapping other passport data descriptors to MCPD.

18-Dates

We will start with the date types that cover:

- Collecting date (**COLLDATE**)
- Acquisition date (**ACQDATE**)

In MCPD the date format is YYYYMMDD where YYYY is the year, MM is the month and DD is the day. Missing data (MM or DD) should be indicated with hyphens or '00' [double zero].

For example an accession that was collected on 04 May 1999 should have a collecting date data as: **19990504**

If the date in your records is June 1999 without the date, then the collecting date should be **19990600** (00 replace the unknown day, and same if the month is unknown too).

To re-format any date format to **19990504** in Excel you can use different methods depending on your original format:

- Find and Replace function:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/find-or-replace-text-and-numbers-on-a-worksheet-0e304ca5-ecef-4808-b90f-fdb42f892e90>

- Text-to-Columns function:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-us/office/split-text-into-different-columns-with-the-convert-text-to-columns-wizard-30b14928-5550-41f5-97ca-7a3e9c363ed7>

followed by a recombination using the Ampersand symbol &:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-gb/office/combine-text-from-two-or-more-cells-into-one-cell-81ba0946-ce78-42ed-b3c3-21340eb164a6>

- Date formatting:

<https://support.microsoft.com/en-au/office/format-a-date-the-way-you-want-8e10019e-d5d8-47a1-ba95-db95123d273e>

19-Geographical coordinates

The MCPD standard allows for geo-coordinates in either decimal or DMS formats. However for the purpose of uploading in Genesys, or for using the geo-data validator tool developed at the Crop Trust, only the decimal format is accepted.

This step will show you how you can reformat your geo-data from DMS (Degrees, Minutes, Seconds) to decimals.

19-Geographical coordinates

Next to the Latitude column you want to reformat, add an extra 6 columns by hovering over the column, clicking **right click** then **Insert**.

Country of origin	Latitude					Longitude	Sto
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Peru	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Peru	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Peru	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Peru	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon
Zambia	S13°8'25.44"					E27°50'57.48"	Lon

In the added columns, you will split the original Latitude column into its basic components: degrees, minutes, seconds and polarity (south or north).

For that purpose, select all the data in the Genus column by clicking on the first row and typing simultaneously **Shift Ctrl down**. Then go to the **Text to columns** tool in Excel, in the **Data** ribbon.

	B	C	D	E	F	G	
1	Country of origin	Latitude				Longitude	Sto
2	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
3	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
4	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
5	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
6	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
7	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
8	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
9	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
10	Peru	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
11	Peru	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
12	Peru	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
13	Peru	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
14	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
15	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon
16	Zambia	S13°8'25.44"				E27°50'57.48"	Lon

19-Geographical coordinates

Clicking on Text to Column will start a dialog box composed of 3 steps that allows you at the end to split your selected data into two columns.

If your latitude data is delimited by a degree sign, comma or any other character then click on Delimited in step 1. In step 2 you select what is the separator of the two columns, in our case it is a degree sign. In step 3 click on Finish.

1

2

3

This splits the degrees from the minutes and seconds. Repeat this process to split the minutes from the seconds using their respective delimiter.

 In the case of the polarity, for example S (south) or N (north), you can also use the **Text to columns** tool, but in step 1 choose **Fixed width** instead.

The resulting columns are as such:

Q	R	S	T
Latitude_polarity	Latitude_degrees	Latitude_minutes	Latitude_seconds
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44
S	13	8	25.44

19-Geographical coordinates

In an adjacent column, you will calculate the absolute value of your decimal latitude, that is because we will add the polarity to it later (negative for South and positive for North).

Use this equation: **=R2+(S2/60)+(T2/3600)** then **click and drag** it across all the column.

Essentially, the decimal latitude is equal to the degrees plus the minutes divided by 60 plus the seconds divided by 3600.

The resulting absolute decimal latitude column looks like this:

S	T	U
Latitude_minutes	Latitude_seconds	Decimal Latitude_absolute
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404
8	25.44	13.1404

Then in another column titled DECLATITUDE (this is your final decimal latitude in MCPD), use this formula:

=IF(Q2="S", Q2*(-1), Q2)

Then drag this formula across all your DECLATITUDE column.

This guide complements the webinar on Passport Data Preparation Part 2. Stay tuned for the following parts that will cover data validation and more mapping to MCPD. If you have any questions about these steps, please send an email to helpdesk@genesys-pgr.org

THE GLOBAL CROP DIVERSITY TRUST

Platz der Vereinten Nationen 7
53113 Bonn
Germany

GENERAL CONTACT

info@croptrust.org

PUBLICATIONS CONTACT

publications@croptrust.org

